

Hardware-Support for Spiking Neural Networks - a look at BrainScaleS-2 and its usage

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ANNs need large amounts of energy for training and inference which is especially critical in low-power environments such as robotics. Getting inspiration from the brain, Spiking Neural Networks are designed to work much more energy-efficiently by communicating through discrete spike events. However, the sparse communication through spikes also creates challenges like the need for translation of static input into dynamic spikes and surrogate gradients to handle the non-differentiability of the spikes. Also, SNNs encode information in time which requires solutions like eligibility traces for credit-assignment during training.

BrainScaleS-2 is a neuromorphic hardware system which allows SNNs to run exceptionally efficiently by providing hardware inspired by the brain's structure. Analog circuits implement a model of the neurons and synapses in the brain, using i.e. the subthreshold behaviour of transistors to model similar neuron dynamics. The analog implementation leads to high energy-efficiency and speed, the neurons are emulated with 1000-fold acceleration compared to biological real-time. The analog components are combined with digital processors which allow flexible interaction with the analog parts.

Software support for BrainScaleS-2 is provided by the python libraries `pynn-brainscales` and `hxtorch`, which provide user-interfaces to define neural networks and train SNNs using functionalities from PyTorch. Training SNNs on BrainScaleS-2 needs to consider the intricacies of the hardware, like the type of synapse used or the size of the chip, which can make partitioning of large networks necessary.

A benchmark for spiking MNIST across neuromorphic hardware shows that BrainScaleS-2 achieves high accuracy while outperforming other similarly-sized hardware in terms of throughput and energy-efficiency.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: neuromorphic computing, spiking neural network, neuromorphic hardware

1 Introduction

In recent years, Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) received a massive gain in popularity. They are used for image generation, chat functionalities especially in the form of Large Language Models (LLMs) like ChatGPT, and in many other applications.

Despite a clear inspiration from the brain, ANNs still differ from it in substantial attributes. A key property of the human brain is its energy efficiency. It operates at roughly 20 Watt [6], as little as a lightbulb.

Training and running inference on ANNs needs huge amounts of resources, especially electricity. Often, highly performant, specialised chips are used. For example the H100 from NVIDIA, which consume roughly 500-600 Watt. [43] As much as 30 brains.

Ranging from an estimated 1,300 MWh for the training of GPT-4, which also consumes approximately 564 MWh per day for inference (that's 17,484 MWh per month), down to 1.5 MWh for the training of the original BERT model from 2019, the power consumption is much higher than the use of the average American household with approximately 0.9 MWh per month. [13, 54, 56]

The brain's efficiency is possible due to its way to process information. Using sparse signals, called spikes, only few neurons are active to process a piece of information. [55]

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This work presents Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) which take inspiration from the brain's mechanisms. Instead of processing continuous signal like ANNs, they process information in the form of spikes. This approach needs changes in the training of the network and the encoding of input and output data, especially if biological realism is a goal.

In order to achieve this sparsity and energy-efficiency for software implementations, special hardware is used. Hardware whose design is inspired by the brain's function and structure is called Neuromorphic Hardware (NH). NH can be purely digital or combine analog and digital components. Generally, it aims to work with low power and support the sparse communication like observed between neurons in the brain. This work provides an introduction to the hardware system BrainScaleS as physical emulation of neurons. BrainScaleS-2 is a partly analog system. We present how synapses and neurons are implemented using analog circuits and how digital components are added to make the system flexible. [45]

1.1 Research Questions

This work aims to provide an introduction into the field of SNNs, NH and the related biology by presenting the foundations of the software, hardware and biology and highlighting how they work together.

Research questions covered in this work are:

- (1) How are SNNs structured and trained and how much biological realism is supported?
- (2) What is the hardware design of BrainScaleS-2 and how does the hardware map to the biological structures?
- (3) How can BrainScaleS-2 be used to train and run an SNN?

1.2 Related Work

An extensive introduction into the attributes of neurons and synapses as well as neuron models and the mathematical formulas to describe them can be found in [28]. [55] provides a more high-level introduction into the most important concepts.

[25] provides an extensive, rather high-level, summary about SNNs. It covers the architecture, challenges regarding input & output encoding as well as different approaches to training. More details about specific learning algorithms can be found in [7, 8, 38] and [63].

BrainScaleS-2 is described by multiple papers in varying detail. [45] focuses on the application of the system, describing how the system can be calibrated to faithfully emulate neuron models and presenting experiments which were conducted using the system. A much deeper look at the hardware implementation is done in [1] and [2], which present details about the circuit design.

2 Biological Background

This chapter provides an overview of the most important aspects about the structure and signal processing in the brain. We focus on the fundamentals which influence the design of SNNs and NH and are essential for questions about biological plausibility. Some biological details and distinctions are left out for the sake of brevity.

2.1 Structure And Signal Processing In The Brain

The brain consists of roughly 100 billion neurons, connected via synapses.

A neuron receives input signals from other neurons, sense organs like the eyes or other sources, processes those signals and maybe sends a signal to other neurons by producing a spike.

If a spike - also called action potential or nerve impulse - is produced, the neuron releases neurotransmitters which travel a short distance from the spiking neuron to the ones connected to it. This small space between the neurons is called synaptic cleft, together with the ends of both the sending and a receiving neuron it forms one synapse. [55] Fig. 1 shows this structure.

Fig. 1. Basic structure of a neuron and synapse, image adapted from [50]

Building the bridge to common data structures, the neurons and synapses form a weighted, directed, graph as shown in Fig. 2. The neurons form the nodes, the synapses the edges of the graph, neurotransmitters travel along the edges.

Internally, each neuron has a specific electric potential. The potential can be increased or decreased when incoming signals from other neurons arrive. Connections (synapses) which cause an increase of the membrane potential are called excitatory. Connections with a decreasing effect on the potential are called inhibitory.

Fig. 2. Neurons forming a weighted, directed graph, image based on [50]

A spike is produced when the neuron's potential reaches its spiking threshold which depends on the previous signals that the neuron received, as well as the timing of those signals and the strength of the synapse where the signal came from.

Fig. 3 shows the membrane voltage (potential) of four neurons with different attributes that influence their spiking behaviour. In the top left, the reset of the membrane potential caused by a spike at 90 and 180 ms can be seen. The vertical lines signal input spikes to the neuron which increase the neurons potential in this case.

Next to changes through spiking, the membrane potential also changes constantly as charged ions diffuse into or out of the neuron. That process is called leak. Without input, a neuron drifts towards its resting potential. This can be seen in the top right in Fig. 3.

The timing of the spikes matters because of the constant movement towards the resting potential, which often goes along with a movement away from the spiking threshold. This makes spikes less likely the more time lies between input signals. Additionally, neurons can adapt their response to input signals in the short term based on previous spikes, either making subsequent spikes more or less likely. This phenomenon is called adaptation. [29, 45] The bottom left of Fig 3 shows how adaptation can cause less spikes.

Next to adaptation, another process called Short-Term Synaptic Plasticity (STSP) influences the strength of the input signals and therefore the effect of repeated input spikes on a neuron. STSP causes subsequent spikes to have stronger or less strong effects on the target neuron, which depends on the availability of the neurotransmitters and vesicles responsible for transporting them. As the name suggests, the effect STSP only lasts a few (milli-) seconds. [30] Fig. 3 shows how STSP can affect the neuron's potential and lead to more spikes.

Fig. 3. Basic structure of a neuron and synapse, image by author.

Additionally to the short-term changes in the neurons, the brain is also capable of changing the synaptic connections between them. This ability is called Long-Term Synaptic Plasticity (LTSP) and results in the creation of new synapses and strengthening or pruning of existing ones. [55]

2.2 Neuron Models

Different neuron models aim to provide mathematical descriptions for the mechanisms described above. The models are not exact descriptions of the biological processes. Instead, they provide abstractions with a different amount of detail, making them suitable depending on the needed degree of biological precision. The two models discussed here use electrical values, like current and voltage, which makes them naturally suited for the use with NH.

2.2.1 Leaky Integrate-And-Fire. The Leaky Integrate-and-Fire (LIF) model works with the fact that neurons always spike in a similar form. Therefore, we cannot transmit information by strength or shape of a spike. Instead, we rely on the occurrence of a spikes and, building upon that, on their timing and frequency.

The change of the neuron's potential over time is modelled to depend on the distance to the resting potential as well as the capacitance-characteristics of the neuron and the current input into it.

One or multiple spikes arrive at the neuron in the form of the input current I which charges the neuron's membrane up to a specific capacity C . The membrane acts as a capacitor, storing the voltage $V(t)$ at time t , and does not keep current indefinitely. Instead, it leaks through the cell membrane, leading to a change in the membrane's potential back to the resting potential V_{rest} . The strength of the leak is characterised by the membrane's resistance R .

$$\tau_m \frac{dV}{dt} = -[V(t) - V_{rest}] + RI$$

This model strongly resembles a resistor-capacitor (RC) circuit, where τ_m describes the RC-constant which is the time needed to charge or discharge the capacitor (the membrane) through the resistor (the border of the membrane) up until a specific amount of voltage.

The model also contains a second term with a reset to V_{reset} after each spike, limiting the model's possibility to accumulate information about successive spikes. [29, 60, 61]

For some simulations it may be no issue to ignore processes like adaptation, which is where a simple model like LIF can be used.

2.2.2 Adaptive Exponential Integrate-And-Fire (AdEx). The main change of the Adaptive Exponential Integrate-And-Fire (AdEx) model compared to the LIF model is the replacement of the static "if above V_{thresh} , then spike" with an exponential term which increases the biological realism.

$$C \frac{dV}{dt} = -g_L [V(t) - V_{rest}] + g_L \Delta_T \exp\left(\frac{V(t) - V_{thresh}}{\Delta_T}\right) - w + I$$

$$\tau_w \frac{dw}{dt} = a[V(t) - V_{rest}] - w$$

At spike time: $V \rightarrow V_{reset}$
 $w \rightarrow w + b$

The first term $-g_L [V(t) - V_{rest}]$ equals the one from the LIF model, calculating the difference to the resting potential V_{rest} , scaled with the leak conductance.

When the membrane's potential represented by the voltage $V(t)$ surpasses the threshold V_{thresh} , the exponential term rises, the lower Δ_T the faster. g_L is the leak conductance, so the inverse of the resistance. A higher conductance means that the membrane is more susceptible to changes, leading to a stronger change through the exponential spike-term and the leak.

Additionally, the AdEx model includes a term for the adaptation w . The term $-w$, combined with the term $\tau_w dw/dt$ for the change of w over time and $w \rightarrow w + b$ for the change caused by spikes, models the adaptation of the neuron. The change by parameter b reflects a neuron's increased or decreased willingness to spike. Apart from spikes, w depends on the membrane's distance to the resting potential, scaled by parameter a . Lastly, I is the input current, like in the LIF model.

A spike also causes the membrane potential to be set to a reset potential V_{reset} , which is shown in the term $V \rightarrow V_{reset}$. [9, 31, 58]

3 Spiking Neural Networks

This chapter describes the architecture of SNNs, covering the main design decisions, the inspiration from biology as well as challenges arising from its structure. A comparison to ANNs is made to highlight the differences. Be aware that this chapter covers only a coarse, basic view of the architecture of ANNs. There are many subforms with various optimisations that differ in implementation details, which we will not pay attention to here.

3.1 Structure Of Neural Networks

The design of Neural Networks (NNs), so ANNs as well as SNNs, is inspired from the structure of our brain. This section explains the connection to the brain's structure and highlights the differences in both architectures.

As described in section 2, the brain's structure can be imagined as a directed graph of neurons. While NN are not necessarily implemented as graphs, the graph structure from the brain still describes their architecture well.

A NN consists of nodes which are connected with each other. We sort the nodes in an NN into three layers. Nodes in the input layer receive the external signal, i.e. text from a user or an image. Nodes in the output layer return the signal that represents the answer of the NN and nodes in the hidden layers forward the signal.

In the body, the output neurons control i.e. speech or movement. In a NN, the activated output nodes determine the predicted word, class, action to perform or anything else the network is trained to produce. In the common case of classification problems, we have one output node per class and train the network to send the strongest signal on the node that is assigned to the expected class. A learnable weight is assigned to each connection between two nodes and is used to scale the input signal. Additionally, each node has a bias, which is a threshold that the node has to reach in order to produce an output activation. During the training of the NN, we aim to find the weights for all connections and biases for all nodes that cause the output nodes to return the expected signals for the training data. Errors in the returned signal compared to the expected one are used to adjust the weights of the connections and the biases of the nodes. [49]

Fig. 4. Overview of ANN concepts, based on [3, 46]

Fig. 4 shows the described structure. Nodes have an activation (darker = stronger) and are connected through edges. Each edge has a weight w and each node a bias b . Providing differently strong inputs to the three input nodes causes an activation of the nodes in the other layers. The Target on the right shows the desired activation of the output layer for the given input. Node a_{32} has an activation which is way too high which means that during training of the NN we need to reduce its activation, as highlighted by the downwards arrow.

3.1.1 Artificial Neural Networks. In ANNs, the weights, biases and node values (activations) are real values. Each input leads to the calculation of an activation for all nodes in the network, in the most basic form of ANNs this is done by multiplying a matrix containing all node-node weights with the vector of activations of layer $k-1$ to calculate the activations in layer k .

For learning, backpropagation is the approach used for many ANNs. First, we calculate the error or cost of the network by taking the activation of all output nodes, comparing it to the desired output, i.e. 1 for the correct class, 0 for all others, and calculating the difference. Fig. 4 shows this with the arrows next to the output nodes. Then we determine how the weights and biases need to be adjusted to reduce the error as much as possible. Updates to the weights in earlier layers happen by sending the error information from the output layer backwards through the network. [32]

3.1.2 Spiking Neural Networks. While the basic structure, nodes which are connected to other nodes via weighted directed edges, is shared, SNNs differ from ANNs in a few major points. First, nodes are either active or not. This reduces the computational effort because the multiplications of weights and activations is reduced to either adding the weight of the edge or not. Second, as the name suggests, SNNs communicate via spikes which are emitted when a node becomes active. This architecture leads to way less processing, as in each time step, the majority of the nodes is not spiking. Due to these mechanism the timing of the spikes plays a huge role in SNNs. Notion of time as a central way of communication in the network also influences how we interpret its output. If we are interested in the spike rate, we need to watch the output nodes for a specific interval before we can determine the prediction of the network. Learning algorithms for SNNs therefore need to consider the continuous time to calculate the error of the network and determine which weights to update. [25] In an ANN we do not have these challenges. Instead, we have discrete time steps dictated by the inputs which are sent to the network.

3.2 Input And Output Codes

In order to train a SNN, we need data to train on. Popular data sets for ANNs like the handwritten numbers in MNIST [39] contain static data, well suited for ANNs, but not for SNNs. We therefore need mechanisms to convert the input data into spikes the SNN can work with. Also, we need to decide how to interpret the spikes of the output nodes, for example considering timing and amount of spikes.

[25] discusses two main types of codes: Rate coding" (How often do the nodes spike?) and Latency or temporal coding (When do they spike?) which are visualised in Fig. 5.

3.2.1 Rate Coding. The use of rate coding is supported by some observed mechanisms in the brain. Research suggests that the visual cortex responds to stronger stimuli with a higher firing rate. [34] Therefore, it seems biological reasonable to apply an input stimulus to the nodes in the input layer in a way that produces the highest spike count in these nodes for the strongest inputs.

Similarly to rate-based input encoding, we can choose the output node with the highest spike count per time interval as the prediction of the network.

3.2.2 Latency Coding. Latency encoding puts more value to the timing of individual spikes, a stronger input stimuli would lead to an earlier spike, a weaker input to a later or no spike at all. To reduce the range of spike-times for a large range of stimuli, a common approach is to apply a logarithmic compression to it, leading to a logarithmic reduction of spike-time for a stronger stimulus. This logarithmic scaling is also supported by biology. Latency codes better match the energy-efficiency of the brain, where a rate-based encoding would require much more energy. [14] We choose the node which spikes first as the networks prediction. "First" is easy to define in the application of SNN, as we have the time of the input as reference. In biology, such a global reference

is hard to find. Instead, we can use the different input stimuli as reference points, for example the time when the visual signal to our eyes changed.

Fig. 5. Different input & output codes, based on [25, Fig. 7]

Both, rate-based and latency-based codes have different strengths and weaknesses.

Latency-based codes are more energy-efficient and faster since we don't need a time-span over which to calculate a rate. However, they are more susceptible to errors or variants and sparse signals may complicate training.

Rate-based codes are quite the opposite. Requiring more energy and possibly more time, they produce more signal to train the network on and missing a single spike has less gravity here. [25]

3.2.3 Further Methods. Delta modulation is concerned with the selection of which data to send to the network rather than how to translate it into spikes. The suggestion is to only send the parts of the input to the network which changed since the last input. For example a section of an image which changed. This approach is also supported by biology, where experiments showed that changing input like a moving object in your field of view produces a stronger input signal. [25]

Population encoding can be combined with the other mechanisms. Instead of relying on only one node, we look at a group of nodes. This can increase the strength of the signal. For example, many nodes can produce a higher rate than one would be able to create. [25] Taking a quick glance at biology, population encoding can be seen as plausible. [44].

3.3 Loss Functions

Loss functions are used to calculate how good the model predicts the desired targets. The higher the loss, the more mistakes were made. We therefore aim to reduce the loss when training the network. The discussed output encodings need to be converted into values interpretable by the loss functions. We focus on Cross-Entropy (CE), which is one commonly used loss function for ANNs.

3.3.1 Rate-Based Codes. Used with rate-based codes, CE aims to reduce the amount of spikes from incorrect classes and treats both, the model's predictions and the expected output, as probability distributions.

As in the training of ANNs, we can use the softmax function to convert the network's outputs into probabilities. p_i is the probability per class i , N_C the number of possible output classes, c_i the spike count for the output node of class i .

The CE L_{ce} can be calculated by multiplying each probability with an element y_i of the one-hot encoded target vector containing a 1 for the correct class.

$$p_i = \frac{e^{c_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_C} e^{c_i}} \quad L_{ce} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_C} y_i \log(p_i)$$

The one-hot encoded target vector can lead to issues if nodes are trained to don't produce spikes anymore because that would essentially remove them from the network. We call this "quiet-node" (or "quiet-neuron") problem.

One way to overcome this is to use the membrane potential as a surrogate for the firing rate, i.e. the sum of all membrane potentials over time. Pushing the output node to a higher membrane potential increases its firing rate.

3.3.2 Latency Codes. Again, the difficulty lies within converting the spike time into a value we can input into the function for CE.

Normally, a stronger signal is interpreted as the model's chosen output i.e. the predicted class. For latency codes this is inverted. A faster signal, so a lower time since the input, signals the prediction of the network. Simple means are enough to handle the inversion, for example reversing the value ($c_i = -s_i$) or calculating the inverse of the latency ($c_i = 1/s_i$).

After inverting, we can input the values c_i calculated based on the spike-time s_i of each output node into the softmax and then into the CE function like done for the spike count c_i above.

Like for the rate-based codes, the membrane potential can again be used as a surrogate, specifying a target voltage $U_i[t]$ per time step t and node i . [25] A higher membrane potential can lead to an earlier spike.

3.4 Challenges For Learning

The last section showed how we can assign a value to the "wrongness" of the networks prediction. This section presents common challenges encountered when using this wrongness to determine necessary updates to the network's parameters and approaches to overcome them. Many presently used learning rules build upon these approaches or encounter similar ones.

3.4.1 Non-Differentiability. Backpropagation is a common way to propagate weight updates from the output layer to earlier layers. To do so, we calculate how much the cost measured at the output layer changes in response to each weight, bias and activation in the previous layer and adjust them in the direction which reduces the cost the most. Mathematically, this is expressed through the gradient of the cost function with respect to those variables. Using the chain rule of differentiation, we then propagate the gradients through the network to update the parameters up until the input layer.

The activations of ANNs are available at every time-step, which makes it easy to calculate their gradients. A big challenge when training SNNs stems from the lack of differentiable signal coming from the discrete spike events found in SNNs. [32]

First steps into the application of backpropagation were made with *SpikeProp* [8] by Bohte et al. They train a network on spike times, so applying latency-based codes. Biologically speaking, a neuron would reset after spiking, causing a sudden change of its membrane potential down to the resting potential. This sudden change means that the derivative of the membrane potential is not well-defined at the point of spiking.

To overcome this "non-differentiability" issue at the spike time, they approximate the change in the membrane potential by a linear function around the spike time. It must be noted that this approach requires each neuron to spike, otherwise no gradient can be calculated and no learning happens. The approximation is shown in Fig. 6, where t_j^a is the spike time and x_j the membrane potential of node j . θ is the threshold, the node spikes when reaching it. Instead of a sudden downwards trend after reaching θ , the linear change is assumed for a small time around t_j^a . [8] This linear approximation is differentiable, so the gradient around the spike time can be calculated, propagated to earlier layers, and the model can be trained on the time when it happens.

Fig. 6. Linear approx. at the spike time used in Spike-Prop, taken from [8]

An alternative approach to solve the non-differentiability is to use surrogate gradients [25]. Again, we want to use the chain rule to calculate the impact of a node's firing behaviour on the loss in order to change the model's parameters accordingly. The amount of spikes per neuron directly depends on its membrane potential, so theoretically we want to calculate the gradient of $\partial S / \partial U$. However, this is non-differentiable, because the spikes are discrete events. The surrogate gradient describes the replacement of this term with a differentiable one on the backward pass, using i.e. the membrane voltage as indicator of the potential spiking activity. Using arctan as defined as default in the python library *snnTorch* [24], we get the following replacement:

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial U} \leftarrow \frac{\partial S_{sub}}{\partial U} = \frac{\frac{1}{\pi} \arctan(\pi U)}{\partial U}$$

3.4.2 Credit Assignment. Backpropagation can be made possible through the solutions for non-differentiability covered in the last section. But it is not biologically realistic. One issue is its reliance on past membrane potentials and spikes from all neurons in order to calculate the weight updates. This conflicts with temporal sparsity which is considered to be present in the brain. [7, 25]

Still, we need to answer the question how much one neuron contributed to the error in the output layer at time t . This is called credit assignment.

Local eligibility traces can be used to answer this question. Instead of globally keeping track of the neuron states, the calculated error is combined with a local trace per neuron that serves as a memory for past spikes. To define a trace, we can use biological dynamics like a decaying exponential after the spike time of an input node. Fig. 7 shows such a possible eligibility trace for a node spiking at the times marked with vertical lines near the x-axis.

This spike-memory describes the neuron's impact on the error, a very recent spike could have been the cause for a wrong spike at the output. This information can be used to determine how

Fig. 7. Exponentially decaying eligibility traces for a neuron spiking four times.

much the weight of the connection to that neuron needs to be adjusted. Errors between $75 \mu\text{s}$ and $158 \mu\text{s}$ will not impact the weight for the connection to the node in Fig. 7 because it is not eligible in those sections. An error at $162 \mu\text{s}$ will lead to a strong weight update.

Using eligibility traces, we can propagate weight updates through the chain of input nodes without the need for global information about the neurons' past states.

3.5 Learning Rules

The last section presented surrogate gradients and eligibility traces as two common building blocks used in learning rules for SNNs. Here, we provide the interested reader a few references to specific learning rules.

A general overview of learning rules and more approaches can be found in [25]. Mathematical details for SpikeProp can be found in [8], learning rules building upon SpikeProp in [38, 63].

How to apply weight updates to the network, especially when considering biological realism, is a topic of active research. To enhance the biological realism, E-Prop does not use direct reverse connections to the input nodes. Instead, connections with random weights to all other nodes are built which results in a biologically more plausible structure.

[7] describes how the model of E-Prop can be extended to capture the adaption occurring in biological nodes which increases the quality of the trained models, adds an reward-based approach, provides mathematical background and presents a comparison against Back-Propagation Through Time (BPTT).

4 Neuromorphic Hardware - BrainScaleS

This chapter presents BrainScaleS-2 as one implementation of NH. It shows how the biological structures and processes in the brain are translated into analog hardware and how the aforementioned parameters of the neurons can be accessed through digital components of the system.

Generally speaking, NH is hardware inspired by the brain's function and structure. Some NH aims to implement a part of the brain's processes with digital hardware. Other NH is (partly) analog, using physical components like capacitors which have attributes that translate well to biological processes in neurons. This is the case for BrainScaleS-2, which is a physical model of the brain. [35, 36]

The first version of BrainScaleS-2 was developed in the context of the BrainScaleS research project funded by the European Union (EU), in the time between 2011 and 2015. [21] From 2013 to 2023, further development took place in the Human Brain Project, a Future and Emerging Technologies Flagship Project from the EU. During the Human Brain Project, the research platform EBRAINS was developed. It provides access to the two neuromorphic hardware systems developed during the project, SpiNNaker (digital) and BrainScaleS version 2. [37] Since version 1 of the system, various improvements like the support of a much higher number of neurons and synapses were made. Further development happens in the EBRAINS 2.0 project running until 2026. [17]

4.1 High-Level Design

The hardware design of BrainScaleS-2 consist of two main segments. As a partly analog system, BrainScaleS-2 combines analog and digital components.

The analog core of the system contains the hardware for the neurons and synapses. Digital processing units extend the analog core. An external Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) is used as link between the BrainScaleS-2 chip and a host computer.

Noteworthy is the fact that BrainScaleS-2 can emulate the biological processes one thousand times faster than biological realtime which is possible due to the low-power analog implementation.

Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 show a high-level view of the single-chip variant of the BrainScaleS-2-system, also called HICANN-X. [47] Fig. 8 shows the symmetric layout of the chip. The 4 quadrants contain the analog circuits for the neurons and synapses. The spike router is responsible for transporting spike events between the neurons. In the top, bottom and the left side, digital processing units are located. Fig. 9 shows a more detailed view of one quadrant, highlighting the matrix structure of the synapse array and providing an overview of the connections between the different segments of the chip.

Central piece of the analog core are the 512 neurons and 131,072 synapses. They are broken into 4 symmetrical sections, 128 neurons and $128 * 256$, so 32,768, synapses each. The synapses are structured as a matrix, each column contains the input synapses for one neuron. Two digital processors, responsible for plasticity and control of the neurons, hence called Plasticity Processing Units, are connected to two synapse matrices each and are located at the top and bottom of the chip. A digital event-routing network connects all components. [45]

Fig. 8. High-Level structure of a single core. The symmetric layout shows 4 synapse arrays, the PPU, neurons and event routing network, taken from [45]

Fig. 9. Structure of one quadrant of the chip, taken from [20]

4.2 Neurons

Each Neuron is made up from a set of sub-circuits, each responsible to implement a specific biological property of the neuron. BrainScaleS-2 implements the AdEx neuron model. Generally speaking, voltages are used to represent the neuron's membrane potential as well as influencing potentials like the leak. Signals between and inside the neurons, i.e. the spikes, are implemented with current flows.

As explained in section 2.2.2, the AdEx model contains the following formulas, using the terms to describe different biological processes.

$$\begin{aligned} C \frac{dV}{dt} &= -g_L [V(t) - V_{rest}] + g_L \Delta_T \exp\left(\frac{V(t) - V_{thresh}}{\Delta_T}\right) - w + I \\ \tau_w \frac{dw}{dt} &= a[V(t) - V_{rest}] - w \\ \text{At spike time:} \quad &V \rightarrow V_{reset} \\ &w \rightarrow w + b \end{aligned}$$

This section describes how some of the biological mechanisms contained in the formula (i.e. spiking, exponential increase, see section 2.1) are implemented in analog circuits.

4.2.1 Exponential Increase. One significant difference between the AdEx and the LIF model is the exponential increase of the membrane potential, described by the term $g_L \Delta_T \exp((V(t) - V_{thresh})/\Delta_T)$.

To implement this, BrainScaleS-2 makes use of the subthreshold behaviour of transistors, which occurs when a transistor receives an input voltage that is below the threshold that causes it to turn on or off. While being technically off, so considered a zero in standard digital circuitry, the transistor still outputs a small drain current. Changing the input voltage linearly causes an exponential change of the drain current, as shown in Fig. 10, exactly the relation described by the exponential in the AdEx term. This current is integrated back onto the neuron's membrane potential, which can be deactivated via a switch, allowing customisation of the neuron's behaviour. [1, 62]

In standard digital circuitry, this subthreshold behaviour is generally not desired and considered as leakage that needs to be worked against. [62] However, BrainScaleS-2 as partly analog system makes use of this intrinsic mechanisms of the used electronic devices to implement the desired biological processes.

Fig. 10. Graph showing the subthreshold exponential increase of the output current, taken from [42].

4.2.2 Spikes, Reset and Refractory Period. While not made explicit in the AdEx formulas, the neuron's ability to spike is central to the model. The circuitry for the spike generation is shown at the top in Fig. 11. This spiking behaviour is implemented with a comparator which receives a threshold voltage V_{thresh} and compares it to the current membrane voltage (or potential) V_{mem} of the neuron. The comparator outputs a logical high when V_{mem} reaches the threshold and holds this signal for a period of time controlled by the variable t_{delay} and a feedback loop to the comparator. [2] This produces a digital voltage pulse, like the spike sent from a biological neuron. [1, 45]

Fig. 11. Circuit diagram of spike circuit (top) and reset with refractory period (bottom), based on [2]

The bottom section in Fig. 11 shows the circuit which implements the reset of the membrane potential back to the resting potential (term $V \rightarrow V_{reset}$ in the formula) and the refractory period. An occurring spike triggers a switch connecting the neurons membrane voltage to a source V_{reset} , which pulls the neuron’s membrane potential to the reset voltage. This is not an instantaneous switch, but is done through an Operational Transconductance Amplifier (OTA), an electronic component which converts the difference between input voltages into an output current (not in the figure). This causes a stronger change when the difference to the reset potential is greater and the conductance of the OTA is therefore higher. [1, 2]

A tuneable bias current I_{refr} together with a capacitor C_{refr} is used to implement the refractory period τ_{refr} , a duration during which the neuron cannot send another spike. Depending on the value of I_{refr} , it takes more or less time until the voltage across the capacitor C_{refr} is high enough to trigger the switch again, disconnecting the reset voltage from the membrane potential. [2] With that, the refractory period ends and the neuron can react to inputs again.

This was another example for the translation of biological processes into the analog neuron implementation of BrainScales-2. The remaining terms of the AdEx model are also implemented in analog circuits, details can be found in appendix A.

4.3 Event Routing And Synapses

This section covers the journey from spike events leaving their neurons, arriving at a synapse and triggering a signal to a post-synaptic neuron.

4.3.1 Sending Spike Events To The Routing Network. Each neuron sends its spike events as a digital voltage pulses. In Fig. 11 this output is labeled *fire*. The event-routing network contains a set of lanes which transport events from a statically assigned subset of 64 neurons.

If a spike occurs in many neurons in one subset simultaneously, a priority encoder chooses the signal to transport first and sends the information about

Fig. 12. Information about simultaneous spike events of four neurons is prioritised and serialised onto one lane, image by author.

the neuron's spike time as well as the neuron's static, 6 bit address to a serialiser, which produces a bit stream for the event. This is shown in Fig. 12, when four neurons spike at the same time. The lane at the bottom contains their addresses ordered by descending priority. In this example, the priority equals the neuron's number (binary encoded).

Now, the spike event from the neuron is available on one lane in the event-routing network. [48]

4.3.2 Receiving Spike Events From The Routing Network. As shown in Fig. 13, the synapses which receive those events are structured as a matrix.

The entry point of the pre-synaptic events are the synapse drivers on the left side in the figure, which are each configured to listen a specific source lane.

One synapse driver can receive events from all neurons in its lane at a time. Those events are combined via temporal multiplexing. This means that the signals from all 64 neurons connected to one synapse driver are not sent sequentially for each neuron after the other, but instead intertwined to increase the efficiency of the routing. In Fig. 13, this is shown by the mixed coloured lines coming out of the synapse driver, one color represents one source neuron in that lane.

After arriving at one row in the synapse matrix, a spike event can be read by all neurons connected to that row. Using a local

6 bit Static Random-Access Memory (SRAM) which stores the neuron address from the synapse's input neuron, each synapse filters those incoming events for the ones sent by the neuron with the matching address. Fig. 14 shows a more detailed view of a synapse. The address in the SRAM can be changed which implements synaptic plasticity. 6 bit are enough to switch between the 64 neurons per lane, as 2^6 equals 64. In the figure, the color of each synapse matches the input spikes it listens to. [45, 47, 48]

4.3.3 Inhibitory And Excitatory Events. As shown in Fig. 13, each synapse driver mirrors its received events to two rows of synapses. One row of synapses is responsible for excitatory, the other one for inhibitory signals to its connected neuron. Excitatory signals cause an increase of the membrane potential, inhibitory signals decrease it.

Each neuron has two vertical input lanes, marked with A and B in Fig. 13. One lane transports the currents for the inhibitory signals, the other one the currents for the excitatory signals, each synapse is only connected to one of the vertical lanes.

This architecture allows one output of a neuron to trigger either type of synapse-signal depending on configuration of the row in which the synapse listening for the event is in. [45]

4.3.4 Weights for Events. Each synapse stores a weight, which is a learnable parameter. The weight is used as a factor for the spike signal and controls its strength. [45] Figure 14 shows the described structure. Each synapse, represented by a square, receives the address of the source event in 'address[5:0]', compares it to its 6 bit listen address stored in local SRAM and, in case of a match, connects its local Digital-to-Analog Converter (DAC) to one of its outputs, which converts the locally stored digital weight of the synapse into an analog signal.

While two outputs are visible in the zoomed in representation of a single synapse on the right, only one of the outputs is used for excitatory or inhibitory signal to the post-synaptic neuron. This is statically configured for the whole row of synapses through the 'sign' input. Therefore, the magnified synapse will always send an inhibitory signal to its post-synaptic neuron. [27]

Fig. 13. The synapse matrix with synapse drivers on the side and neurons on the bottom, based on [20]

Fig. 14. Structure of the synapse array and detail for a single synapse, based on [20]

4.3.5 Correlation Sensors. The right part of the synapse circuit in Fig. 14 shows the correlation sensor, which measures correlation and anti-correlation. The correlations refer to the time between a pre-synaptic spike and a following post-synaptic spike, a lower time signals a higher possibility that the input spike triggered a spike in the post-synaptic neuron. The anti-correlations refer to the opposite direction, measuring the time between a post-synaptic spike and a pre-synaptic spike occurring afterwards.

Spike-Time Dependent Plasticity (STDP) describes the biological process that synapses adapt based on these correlations between pre- and postsynaptic spikes.

One correlation sensor is located at each synapse where it directly reads the information about pre-synaptic spikes. The postsynaptic spikes generated by the neuron in a column can be read by its input synapses through vertical connections from the neuron to all synapses in the column. In Fig. 14 this is shown by an arrow labelled *post*.

Once a postsynaptic spike reaches the synapse, the correlation sensor calculates the time difference to the last presynaptic spike and stores it in form of a voltage. [27, 45]

4.4 Digital Components

The last section answered the question how the biological model of the neurons and synapses can be translated into hardware, showing analog circuits which implement the mechanisms described by the AdEx model. It also highlighted examples where the analog components of BrainScaleS-2 are beneficial for the implementation of biological processes. However, in order to use this "brain in silicon" to run and train SNNs we need a way to interact with it.

This access is made possible through two digital processors, called Plasticity Processing Units (PPUs), which are responsible for plasticity algorithms and control of the neurons. The PPUs are connected to two synapse matrices each and located at the top and bottom of the chip. The PPUs are the digital counterpart to the analog core we just covered. Providing a flexible digital architecture, they extend and build upon the analog circuits for multiple use cases which will be covered in this section.

Information present in the analog core are the correlations, as described at the end of the previous section, as well as values of neurons like their membrane potential, which can be used as surrogate gradient for spikes like described in section 3.3. [2, 27, 45]

4.4.1 Programmable Hybrid Plasticity. The "hybrid" in hybrid plasticity refers to the combination of digital calculations and analog measurements. One important analog measurement are the (anti-)correlations between pre- and postsynaptic spikes.

The transfer of these analog values to the PPU is done via a Column Analog-to-Digital Converter (CADC) which is able to read the values from all 256 columns in the synaptic matrix at the same time. Using Single Instruction, Multiple Data (SIMD) units in the PPU, these values can be used as inputs to efficiently calculate parameter updates when training SNNs. Increasing the efficiency, it is possible to read the next row (of the 256 overall) while the previous values are still processed for weight updates.

The decision to implement highly parallel access to the synapses, i.e. for computing weight updates, was made with biological realism in mind. Biologically realistic models used for calculating weight updates use information local to each synapse which makes the parallel processing efficient because the calculations for each synapse can run independently. [27] The weight updates can even happen with the help of machine learning models, because the PPU's have a general-purpose part next to the structure optimised for synapse access which can be used for such computation.

Fig. 15 provides an overview of the components of the PPU. Supported by memory and a cache, the processing can happen in the general purpose part or the specialised vector units which have a direct connection to the synapse matrix through the IO unit.

4.4.2 In-The-Loop Learning. In-the-loop learning refers to the approach of reading information from a model, the analog neurons and synapses in this case, and using these information to generate input to that same model. The loop therefore exists, because the model's output influences its input.

Closing the loop is made possible by simulating the environment on the general-purpose part of the PPU's. Reading the spike signals from the neurons, the simulated environment can react on it, for example by moving through a landscape when a motor neuron spikes. These changes of the environment can then be fed back to the SNN by inserting spike signals. [45] Apart from the mentioned correlation information, the PPU's can also read information from the neuron circuits like their membrane potential as well as insert spikes into the event routing network.

Fig. 15. Components of the PPU, taken from [27]

4.5 A Wafer Scale System

So far, this section gave insights into the different analog and digital parts of a single BrainScaleS-2 chip. One single chip only provides limited computational resources, so in order to be able to simulate larger networks, a combination of multiple chips is desired.

At the time of this work, BrainScaleS-2 is only available as single chip system on EBRAINS. However, the previous version of BrainScaleS-2, BrainScaleS version 1, is available as a wafer-scale system, shown in Fig. 16. [16] In the wafer-scale system, around 400 single BrainScaleS-1 chips which are printed on a wafer are combined with an additional connectivity layer directly on the same wafer.

Fig. 16. Wafer containing ca. 400 BrainScaleS-1 chips, taken from [16]

For BrainScaleS-1, 20 of those wafer-scale systems are deployed together with commodity hardware, i.e. for monitoring and access-management, creating a system containing around 4 million neurons, 512 per chip, as shown in Fig. 17.

For BrainScaleS-2, development towards such a wafer-scale system was presented in 2021, as well as strategies which would allow reuse of existing BrainScaleS-1 modules. [33]

Fig. 17. Full system with 20 BrainScaleS-1 modules, taken from [15]

5 SNNs On BrainScaleS

This chapter combines the software and the hardware from the previous chapters.

We present PyNN and hxtorch as software interfaces and see how a small SNN can be trained.

5.1 Accessing BrainScaleS through PyNN

PyNN (pronounced pine) is a python library which can be used to interact with various neuron / network simulators and NH.

The authors of PyNN describe it's main goal as "Write the code for a model once, run it on any supported simulator or hardware device *without modification*" [12].

It is open source, having a history in GitHub which dates back to 2007. [11]

PyNN was created to solve issues arising with the vast diversity in available simulators and NH. Those issues include difficult reproducibility, as researchers would need to manually translate provided code between simulators.

Still, the diversity in simulators and NH is not only disadvantageous. Instead, the high diversity allows researches to pick the right tool for the job as each backend has different strengths regarding supported functionality, scalability or usability. Additionally, the same experiment can be run on different backends to verify the results. [12]

In order to solve the translation issues, PyNN serves a layer of abstraction above the different supported backends. Users can create neurons and synapses via high-level definitions, which are translated into the classes, attributes including units, functions and parameters from the selected

backend. The python library `pynn-brainscales` [53] provides neuron and synapse definitions which are compatible with the high level abstractions provided by PyNN while providing access to the hardware parameters of BrainScaleS-2.

```

1 import pynn_brainscales.brainscales2 as sim
2
3 # create a neuron with enabled adaptation
4 adex_neuron = sim.Population(size=1, cellclass=sim.cells.HXNeuron(
5     adaptation_enable=True
6 ))
7 # create a LIF neuron with a custom reset voltage
8 lif_neuron = sim.Population(size=1, cellclass=sim.cells.HXNeuron(reset_v_reset=-42))
9
10 sim.Projection(
11     # connect both neurons ...
12     lif_neuron, lif_neuron, connector=sim.AllToAllConnector(),
13     # ... using a synapse
14     synapse_type=sim.synapses.StaticSynapse(weight=42)
15 )

```

Listing 1. Creation of neuron and synapses using PyNN

This example shows the high level of abstraction provided by PyNN. We define a `Population` of neurons with the same type instead of single neurons. We also define the synapse in form of a `Projection`, which connects two groups (populations) of possibly thousands of neurons through the same synapse type. `pynn-brainscales` provides the BrainScaleS-2-specific neuron implementations, working together with common PyNN structures like the `AllToAllConnector` or the `Population`.

`pynn-brainscales` covers the user-facing part of access to BrainScaleS-2. The translation of the attributes of the `HXNeuron` into hardware-configuration is done by more low-level libraries, written in C++. An overview about those libraries is provided in appendix B.

The defined class `HXNeuron` gives the user access to hardware parameters. It is worth to note, that these parameters need to be scaled correctly in order to match the values read out from the chip. [19] More about this challenge can be read in appendix C.

5.2 Training a SNN on BrainScaleS-2

This section covers the training of SNNs on BrainScaleS-2, presenting benefits of BrainScaleS-2 but also encountered challenges.

5.3 Training A Single Neuron

This section uses a simple example to present which core challenges exist in the training of a (minimal) SNN on BrainScaleS-2 and how they can be overcome. It does not cover the whole training, because this would exceed the scope of this work. The example presented here was taken from the BrainScaleS-2 documentation by the Electronic Vision(s) Team [22], where the interested reader finds all information about the training.

5.3.1 The Target. Given are the spikes of a neuron which receives inputs from 25 other neurons. The goal is to train a new neuron which starts with random weights for the synapses to

the 25 input neurons to spike at the same times as the target neuron. Fig. 18 shows the membrane potential of the target neuron and the timings of the input spikes as vertical lines near the x-axis. The trained output neuron should match the four spike times as close as possible.

5.3.2 Calculating The Weight Update. How much did one of the 25 input neurons contribute to a missing spike at time t ? One approach to answer this question was presented in section 3.4.2, covering local eligibility traces. This example combines these eligibility traces for the input neurons with a surrogate gradient for the target spikes, which are again discrete events. Then, the eligibility of each input neuron can be combined with the surrogate gradient to determine how much impact a weight change potentially has on the spiking behaviour. [22]

Fig. 19 visualises the idea. Graph a) shows the surrogate gradient for the trainable output neuron spiking at $t = 80$ with an exponentially increasing membrane potential beforehand. Graph b) shows the eligibility trace of one input neuron, which spikes two times at $t = 10$ and $t = 70$. Graph c) shows the result of multiplying the eligibility with the surrogate gradient.

Fig. 18. Spikes from input nodes (vertical lines) and membrane potential of target neuron, based on [22]

Fig. 19. Combination of surrogate gradient and eligibility trace to determine magnitude of weight update, image by author.

Due to the high distance between the input spike at $t = 10$ and the output spike at $t = 80$, the product of the surrogate gradient and the eligibility ($SG * \text{elig.}$) at $t = 10$ is very small. For the second spike at $t = 70$ the product is much higher, because changing the weight of the synapse to the input neuron will impact the output neuron 10 time steps before it spikes. A strong weight increase here may trigger the spike immediately as the membrane potential of the target neuron is already high.

5.3.3 Weighted Synapses. The synapses in our network can have positive and negative weights. As explained in section 2.1, synapses with a negative impact on the postsynaptic neuron are called inhibitory, positively impacting synapses are called excitatory.

BrainScaleS-2 implements those connections in hardware by defining signed rows in the synapse array (section 4.3.3).

Our network can therefore not simply set a negative or positive weight for any synapse. Excitatory synapses only allow positive, inhibitory negative weights. This means that for each of the 25 input neurons, we have to define two synapses to the output neuron. The following Listing creates this network with PyNN.

```

1 # output population
2 pop_output = pynn.Population(1, pynn.cells.HXNeuron())
3 pop_output.record(["spikes", "v"])
4
5 # input population
6 pop_input = pynn.Population(25, pynn.cells.SpikeSourceArray(spike_times=[]))
7
8 # define two projections (excitatory + inhibitory) to allow signed weights
9 synapse_exc = pynn.standardmodels.synapses.StaticSynapse(weight=42)
10 synapse_inh = pynn.standardmodels.synapses.StaticSynapse(weight=-42)
11
12 projection_io_inh = pynn.Projection(pop_input, pop_output, pynn.AllToAllConnector(),
13                                     synapse_type=StaticSynapse(weight=42), receptor_type="inhibitory")
14 projection_io_exc = pynn.Projection(pop_input, pop_output, pynn.AllToAllConnector(),
15                                     synapse_type=synapse_exc, receptor_type="excitatory")

```

Listing 2. Definition of the input and output population and synapses, taken from [22].

When updating the weights during training, we need to assign the signed weights to the respective projection. During training, this can lead to connections being removed, i.e. if the connection between neurons started with a positive weight but was changed to a negative one. This dynamic adjustment resembles plasticity mechanisms in the brain. [55]

The calculation of the desired weight updates and adjustment of the synapse weights is managed through the PPU's as described in section 4.4.1.

This covers a few core aspects of the training of a very minimal SNN on BrainScaleS-2 using PyNN, calculating the parameters of the analog components to resemble a target spiking pattern. Eligibility traces and surrogate gradients can be combined to determine the magnitude of weight updates, which are calculated on the digital parts of the system. BrainScaleS-2 supports high flexibility in the configuration of the analog circuits, but the used signed weights must respect the structure of the synapse matrix on the BrainScaleS-2 chip. The configuration of the network with respect to this hardware structure is possible via PyNN.

5.4 Training A SNN For MNIST

We now cover a more complex example, looking at the challenges arising during the training of a larger model which classifies the images from the MNIST dataset. MNIST contains 28 by 28 pixel sized grey scale images of handwritten digits between zero and nine. [39]

Again, this section only highlights challenges and opportunities which arise due to the nature of SNNs and BrainScaleS-2 and not cover all details of the training. It is also based on an example from the Electronic Vision(s) Team [23], so interested readers can see the full example there.

5.4.1 Input Encoding. The MNIST dataset contains static images of the handwritten digits. As described in section 3.2, we need to convert this data into dynamic input for the SNN.

We use latency coded inputs to translate the input pixel values into a series of input spikes in a time interval T . Darker pixels cause an early spike, lighter ones a later spike. Fig. 20 shows one image from MNIST on the left and the generated spikes for three timesteps. The darker center causes earlier spikes than the lighter edges of the digit.

Fig. 20. Latency encoding of a handwritten four from MNIST. Light grey pixels show the full digit for reference, black the pixels which trigger spikes in each timestep, image by author.

5.4.2 Handling A Large Network. The network needed for MNIST is much larger than our 26 neuron example from the last section.

The BrainScaleS-2 hardware cannot be scaled as easily as standard hardware, i.e. by adding more RAM. Partitioning the network allows us to train large SNNs on BrainScaleS-2 by splitting the network into small enough partitions which are simulated sequentially.

As presented in section 4.1, a single BrainScaleS-2 chip contains 512 neuron circuits with 256 incoming synapses each. Using half of the synapses for inhibitory connections with a negative weight and the other half for positive weights, we are left with 128 inputs per neuron (see Fig. 13). If we need more incoming connections per neuron, we can combine multiple neuron circuits to one compound neuron, increasing the possible amount of incoming connections, but reducing the number of possible neurons on the chip. [23]

For the MNIST classification task, we structure the network as follows: 784 ($28 \cdot 28$) neurons are used for the input layer, one per pixel in the image. The output layer contains 10 neurons, one per class. The hidden layer is made of 256 neurons, this size is variable and one parameter that can influence the model's quality. All in all, we have $784 + 256 + 10 = 1,050$ neurons.

The neurons will be densely connected, so all input neurons to all hidden neurons and all hidden neurons to all output neurons. This leaves us with $784 \cdot 256 \cdot 10 = 2,007,040$ synapses.

The scale of the network largely exceeds the capacity of the chip.

Each neuron circuit can receive 128 input connections. We have to calculate how many neuron circuits have to be combined to handle all incoming connections from the previous layer. N_i denotes the number of neurons in layer i , starting with the input. C_i is the number of neuron circuits which need to be combined in layer i .

Then, we need to determine how many of the C_i compound neurons fit onto the chip, denoted by N_i^{BS} , and how many partitions p_i are needed for all neurons N_i . [23]

$$C_i = \left\lceil \frac{N_{i-1}}{128} \right\rceil \quad N_i^{BS} = \left\lfloor \frac{512}{C_i} \right\rfloor \quad p_i = \left\lceil \frac{N_i}{N_i^{BS}} \right\rceil$$

As example, we need to connect $\lceil 784/128 \rceil = 7$ neuron circuits for the neurons in the hidden layer in order to receive input from the 784 input nodes. For convenience, [23] uses 8 circuits per compound neuron. $\lfloor 512/8 \rfloor = 64$ neurons of this size fit onto the BrainScaleS-2 chip. Therefore, we need $\lceil 256/64 \rceil = 4$ partitions for the hidden layer.

This partitioning works, because the model we defined is a feedforward model. This means that signal is only propagated from input to output, not between neurons in the same layer and not backwards. Therefore, we can simulate the different partitions of one layer sequentially and concatenate the results.

Looking back at the biology, this can be considered partly realistic. In the brain, information is not solely propagated in a feedforward manner. The brain contains some recurrent connections, building loops with earlier nodes in the input path. [7] Modelling such recurrent networks on the restricted space of the BrainScaleS-2 chip only works like described above if the largest recurrent subnetwork fits onto the chip. [23]

5.4.3 Training. The 26 neuron example showed that we can successfully train a small SNN with PyNN, calculating errors and updating weights of the projections manually. For a network of the size we have now this would be rather inconvenient.

A commonly used python library for training ANNs is PyTorch, which provides a high-level interface to define and train neural networks, as well as implementations for common loss functions and support for automatic gradient calculation like needed for backpropagation. [4] To enable an easier, PyTorch-like training experience, the Electronic Vision(s) Group developed the library `hxtorch`. `hxtorch` uses data structures from PyTorch and the same C++ libraries as `pynn-brainscales` to interact with the hardware. [51]

The following Listing sketches how `hxtorch` and PyTorch are combined to define and train the SNN on BrainScaleS-2. We see that classes and functions from both libraries can be used together, `hxtorch` provides the access to the hardware, i.e. neurons and synapses, while PyTorch contains functionality to run the model and apply weight updates.

```

1 import torch
2 import hxtorch.spiking as hxsnn
3
4 # build network using hxtorch, as subclass from PyTorch Module class
5 class SNN(torch.nn.Module):
6     for i in range(4): # we need 4 partitions for the hidden layer
7         hidden = Synapse(
8             in_features=784, # from input layer
9             out_features=64, ...) # one hidden layer partition
10        neuron = hxsnn.LIF(size=64, ...) # use the LIF model for the neurons
11
12 network = SNN()
13
14
15 # loss function from PyTorch, based on the same formula as CE (section 3.3)
16 loss_func = torch.nn.functional.nll_loss
17
18 for data, target in training_data_with_labels:
19     scores = model(data.to(network.device)) # run model via PyTorch
20
21     loss = loss_func(scores, target.to(model.network.device)) # compute loss
22     loss.backward() # apply backpropagation

```

Listing 3. Usage of `hxtorch` and PyTorch to build and train a SNN, based on [23] (simplified).

5.4.4 Performance. Using the support for partitioning, which was introduced in [5] earlier this year, BrainScaleS-2 can be used to train a model for the 28 by 28 pixel variant of MNIST. Previously, a 16 by 16 pixel variant of MNIST was used due to the size constraints. Fig. 21 shows a comparison of benchmark results on different NH in their accuracy and performance when classifying this 16 by 16 pixel variant, made by the researchers developing BrainScaleS-2 [10].

	Platform	Reference	Architecture	Node, nm	Accuracy, %	Energy/inference, μJ	Throughput, inference $\times \text{s}^{-1}$	Latency, μs	
Digital	SpiNNaker	Stromatias et al. (61)	784-500-500-10	130	95.0	/ [*]	/ [*]	/	
			TrueNorth	Esser et al. (62)	CNN (1 ensemble)	28	92.7	0.27	1,000
	—	Chen et al. (63)	CNN (16 ensembles)	28	95	4	1,000	/	
			CNN (64 ensembles)	28	99.4	108.0	1,000	/	
			236-20	10	88.0	1.0	6,250	/	
			784-1024-512-10	10	98.2	12.4	/	/	
			784-1024-512-10	10	97.9	1.7	/	/	
			MorphIC	Frenkel et al. (64)	784-500-10 [†]	65	97.8	205	/
	Analog	SPOON	Frenkel et al. (38)	784-500-10 [†]	65	95.9	21.8	250	/
				CNN	28	97.5	0.3 [‡]	/	117
BSS-1		Schmitt et al. (56)	100-15-15-5	180	95.0	/ [*]	10,000	/	
BSS-2		Göltz et al. (57)	256-246-10	65	96.9	8.4	21,000	< 10	
BSS-2	This work	256-246-10	65	97.6	2.4	85,000	8		

^{*} Estimates were given by Pfeiffer and Pfeil (40).

[†] Segmented input and hidden layers.

[‡] Based on presilicon estimates.

Fig. 21. Comparison of MNIST benchmark results across neuromorphic platforms, taken from [10]

The model trained on BrainScaleS-2 uses 512 neurons, filling the whole chip. It classified 97.6% of the test images correctly, 1.8% less than the best accuracy which was achieved on the custom digital neuromorphic system TrueNorth by using an ensemble of 64 Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), a model architecture particularly well suited for visual processing, each consisting of 3,840 neurons. [26]

Looking at the energy-efficiency, one must consider the size of the used technology nodes, smaller nodes are more energy efficient. Comparing BrainScaleS-2 to nodes of the same size, we see that the most efficient digital system uses 9 times as much energy as BrainScaleS-2.

For throughput, the performance of BrainScaleS-2 is unmatched. It is able to classify 13.6 times as much images per seconds as the most performant run on a digital platform.

This benchmark highlights the benefits of combining analog with digital hardware. The analog implementation of the neurons and synapses leads to a high energy-efficiency and processing speed, highlighted by the throughput. The digital components allow a flexible implementation of learning rules using information from the analog components, which enables the successful training of SNNs.

6 Summary

This work gave an introduction into our current understanding of signal processing in the brain, describing the biological mechanisms and highlighting the relevant attributes of neurons and synapses used in the LIF and AdEx model.

How these parameters and mechanisms can be translated into analog circuits was discussed using the BrainScaleS-2 system as one example for neuromorphic hardware. BrainScaleS-2 uses the physical attributes of the hardware to implement desired biological properties and combines these analog circuits with digital components. The partly analog implementation leads to a high

energy efficiency and fast simulation, allowing emulation of the neurons with 1000-fold acceleration compared to biological real-time. The digital components add flexibility to the system, i.e. for simulating training environments for SNNs.

SNNs were presented as energy-efficient, biologically more realistic alternative to ANNs, enabling solutions in low-power areas like embedded systems and facilitating brain-research with the possibility to simulate biologically plausible learning algorithms, especially efficiently when using neuromorphic hardware. However, training of SNNs comes with unique challenges due to the discrete nature of spike events and the operation in continuous time. Solutions like surrogate gradients and eligibility traces were presented for the challenges during training.

Lastly, the biological attributes, translated into hardware, were configured using PyNN and hxtorch to interact with BrainScaleS-2. Training the SNNs highlighted challenges, like the limited size of the chip and the mapping of properties of the SNNs to hardware. Inhibitory and excitatory synapses were used to implement weighted connections in an SNN and partitioning was presented as a solution to train larger-than-chip SNNs. Results from spiking MNIST showed that a SNN on BrainScaleS-2 can achieve competitive accuracy, especially considering the low power consumption and high throughput.

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Use of AI: OpenAI's GPT-4 and GPT-5 (ChatGPT) was used to gather ideas, challenge the author's understanding and to get an overview about the discussed topics as well as areas for further research. Output of those conversations were keywords for further research, papers to read and summaries of the topic's basics. The author verified all information through independent sources, as marked in text. No part of this work was generated by AI.

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A Analog Implementation Of AdEx Model

This section covers the implementation of the AdEx terms not covered in section 4.2.

A.0.1 Adaptation. Adaptation describes the neuron’s behaviour on fast, subsequent spikes, making additional spikes either more or less likely. Figure 22 shows the main components of the circuit.

Using an OTA, the circuit responsible for adaptation reads the difference between the membrane potential V_{mem} ($V(t)$ in the formula) and generates a current which affects the spiking response. The generated current is then integrated onto V_{mem} , if positive, this increases the membrane’s potential, making subsequent spikes easier. If negative, subsequent spikes get limited. In the AdEx formula, this process is described via the term $-w$.

A different part of the circuit implements the updates to the adaption term w . Originally, the changes are described by $w \rightarrow w + b$, which is caused by spikes of the neuron, and $\tau_w \frac{dw}{dt} = a[V(t) - V_{rest}] - w$, which models the change to w over time.

The value of w is stored as the voltage V_w . When a spike occurs, this value is modified by a charge pump, a circuit which is able to change the voltage of a connected capacitor. The effect of the pump can be controlled via the configurable input current I_w , which either reduces or increases V_w on every spike event which occurs. Apart from updates through spikes, V_w changes based on the difference to the membrane potential $V(t)$. This is also implemented using an OTA, which receives the membrane current as input. The OTA is combined with a tuneable conductance g_w that can be used to control the strength of the change to w .

Applying those adjustments to the hardware, the adaptation terms in the AdEx model are replaced with a current- and capacitance-based equivalent.

$$\tau_w \frac{dw}{dt} = a[V(t) - V_{rest}] - w$$

is replaced by $-C_w \frac{dV_w}{dt} = g_w(V_w - V(t))$, using $w = a(V_w - V_{rest})$

The adaptation can be disabled via a switch en_{adapt} , making the system flexible to implement different neuron models. [1, 40, 57]

Fig. 22. Simplified circuit diagram for the described adaptation terms, based on [1, 2]

A.0.2 Leak. The leak, which is defined by the term $g_L[V(t) - V_{rest}]$ of the AdEx model, is built very simply by using a single OTA.

The OTA receives two inputs, the current membrane voltage $V(t)$ and the leak potential, which we consider equal to the resting potential V_{rest} here.

If the membrane voltage is higher than the resting potential, the generated output current from the OTA is negative, pulling the membrane down to the resting potential. Otherwise, if $V_{leak} > V(t)$, the output current is positive. The strength of the current depends on the difference between the voltages, implementing a higher leak the farther away the neuron's potential is from the resting potential. Analog to the other circuits, the leak can be detached from the neuron circuit through a switch. [2, 59]

A.0.3 Input Current. The last part of the AdEx formulas is the input current I . It consist on an excitatory and an inhibitory current, which the neuron receives from its input synapses.

The currents are integrated on the neuron's membrane current V_{mem} .

B Accessing The Hardware Of BrainScaleS

The following figure shows an overview of the different software components involved in accessing the hardware of BrainScaleS-2.

Fig. 23. Overview of the BrainScaleS-2 software, taken from [41]

The entry points for the user are provided by PyNN, as shown in the section 5.1, and by hxtorch, a library for the training of SNNs on BrainScaleS-2. hxtorch was used for spiking MNIST in section 5.4.3.

When focusing on the configuration of hardware parameters, we can concentrate on the software stack in the Hardware Abstraction layer.

LoLa (Logical Layer) provides a logical view of the hardware, for example by grouping the different values in the analog parameter store in form of an `AtomicNeuron`, [41] which is created through the `HXNeuron` we define in PyNN. The `AtomicNeuron` class in LoLa contains all hardware-parameters which we can configure.

Setting the hardware parameters means that we have to access the correct rows and columns in the synapse matrix or the neuron space to set i.e. the synapse weight in the local SRAM. This access is managed through HALCO, which is the coordinate layer. It provides a coordinate system for BrainScaleS-2 which enables other software components to access the rows and columns. [41, 52]

It can be seen that instead of one big module that is responsible for the full hardware access, many small, specialised C++ modules are used. This provides flexibility to replace and enhance modules, which keeps the system adaptable to advances in the hardware development.

C Calibrating Neuron Parameters

The BrainScaleS-2 documentation states that the hardware units do not relate to the biological units. Also, the hardware units do not translate into measurable voltages or currents on the chip and have different meanings across circuits. This means, that setting the value of `threshold_v_threshold` to 400 (no unit) does not mean that you will see the neuron spiking when its plotted value for the membrane potential reaches 400 a.u. (arbitrary units) read out from the hardware. Also, setting `leak_v_leak` to 300 does not mean that the leak is actually lower than the spiking threshold. [18] This complicates the definition of the high level abstractions, especially because the neuron models should behave the same as on simulators.

To show an example, the code on the left sets the parameters for a `HXNeuron` which is simulated using PyNN. (Full code in appendix C.1.) The plot on the right shows the membrane potential of the neuron roughly steady at 400 a.u. The values for the voltages are read out from the CADCs and do not match the parameter values passed to PyNN. The leak is set to a higher value than the threshold, so we would expect the neuron to increase its membrane potential until it spikes.

```

1 neuron = pynn.cells.HXNeuron(
2     leak_v_leak = 600,
3     threshold_v_threshold = 450,
4     reset_v_reset = 150,
5
6     // additional parameters
7 )

```

Listing 4. Creation of `HXNeuron`

Fig. 24. A `HXNeuron` on BrainScaleS-2 with a plot of measured voltages

This mismatch can be solved by converting the software parameters based on how they relate to the membrane measurement values. The conversion was done with an example notebook provided by the Electronic Vision(s) team. [19] (Code for neuron in appendix C.2) The plot shows that the neuron parameters now lead to the correct behaviour, a "leak-over-threshold" neuron, where the leak mechanism causes the neuron's membrane potential to increase high enough to cause a spike.

```

1 def inverse(x):
2     return (x - par[1]) / par[0]
3 // params for inverse (par):
4 // th_m2s : [1.01, 137.27]
5 // leak_m2s : [0.77, -76.21]
6 // reset_m2s : [0.84, -150.24]
7
8 neuron = pynn.cells.HXNeuron(
9     leak_v_leak = leak_m2s(600),
10    threshold_v_threshold = th_m2s(450),
11    reset_v_reset = th_m2s(150), // ...
12 )

```

Listing 5. Creation of `HXNeuron`

Fig. 25. A `HXNeuron` on BrainScaleS-2 with a plot of measured voltages

C.1 Code For HXNeuron Without Calibration

This code is strongly inspired from [19].

```
1 import pynn_brainscales.brainscales2 as pynn
2 from _static.common.helpers import setup_hardware_client, get_nightly_calibration
3
4 setup_hardware_client()
5 calib = get_nightly_calibration()
6 pynn.setup(initial_config=calib)
7
8 neuron = pynn.cells.HXNeuron(
9     leak_v_leak = 600,
10    reset_v_reset = 150,
11    threshold_v_threshold = 450,
12
13    threshold_enable = True,
14    refractory_period_refractory_time = 255,
15    membrane_capacitance_capacitance = 63,
16
17    leak_i_bias = 150,
18    reset_i_bias=1022,
19    reset_enable_multiplication=True
20 )
21 pop = pynn.Population(1, neuron)
22
23 pop.record(["v", "spikes"])
24
25 pynn.run(0.2)
26
27 plot_membrane_dynamics(pop, ylim=(100, 800))
28 plt.axhline(450, color='orange', label='v_threshold')
29 plt.axhline(150, color='blue', label='v_reset')
30 plt.axhline(600, color='green', label='v_leak')
31
32 plt.legend()
33 plt.show()
34
35 pynn.end()
```

Listing 6. Creation of a HXNeuron using uncalibrated parameter values

C.2 Code For HXNeuron With Calibration

The full code which performs the calculation of the calibration values can be found in [19]. The main idea behind the calculation is to sweep possible input values, get the membrane measurements and then do a least squares polynomial fit using `numpy.polyfit()`. This is how the values for the `inverse()` function were determined.

Here, we just show the code for the neuron definition and the plot in Fig. 25.

```

1 pynn.setup(initial_config=calib)
2
3 v_leak = v_leak_m2s(600)
4 v_threshold = v_th_m2s(450)
5 v_reset = v_reset_m2s(150)
6
7 pop = pynn.Population(1, pynn.cells.HXNeuron(
8     leak_v_leak = v_leak,
9     reset_v_reset = v_reset,
10    threshold_v_threshold = v_threshold,
11
12    threshold_enable = True,
13    refractory_period_refractory_time = 255,
14    membrane_capacitance_capacitance = 63,
15
16    leak_i_bias = 150,
17    reset_i_bias=1022,
18    reset_enable_multiplication = True
19 ))
20
21 pop.record(["v", "spikes"])
22
23 pynn.run(0.2)
24 plot_membrane_dynamics(pop, ylim=(100, 800))
25
26 plt.axhline(600,color='green',label=f'v_leak ({int(v_leak_s2m(v_leak))} a.u.)')
27 plt.axhline(
28     450,color='orange',label=f'v_threshold ({int(v_th_s2m(v_threshold))} a.u.)')
29 plt.axhline(150,color='blue',label=f'v_reset ({int(v_reset_s2m(v_reset))} a.u.)')
30
31 plt.legend()
32 plt.show()
33
34 pynn.end()

```

Listing 7. Creation of a HXNeuron using calibrated parameter values